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MISLEADING STATEMENTS, EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES AND CONCLUSIONS IN THE PAPER ENTITLED "THE M-PHASE REGULATORY PHOSPHATASE PP2A-B55 δ OPPOSES PROTEIN KINASE A ON ARPP19 TO INITIATE MEIOTIC DIVISION" AUTHORED BY LEMONNIER, T., MARIA DALDELLO, E., POULHE, E., TRAN LE, T., MIOT, M., JESSUS, C. AND DUPRÉ, A. AND PUBLISHED IN BIORXIV [BIORXIV (2019) DOI: [HTTP://DX.DOI.ORG/10.1101/810549](http://dx.doi.org/10.1101/810549)]

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Abstract. The paper entitled "The M-phase regulatory phosphatase PP2A-B55 δ opposes protein kinase A on Arpp19 to initiate meiotic division", authored by Lemonnier, T., Maria Daldello, E., Poulhe, E., Tran Le, T., Miot, M., Jesus, C. and Dupré, A., and published in the Journal BioRxiv [bioRxiv (2019) doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1101/810549>] purported to show that the protein phosphatase that dephosphorylated serine 109 Arpp19 phosphorylated by PKA was PP2A-B55 δ and that the dephosphorylation reaction was responsible for progesterone induced resumption of meiosis in *Xenopus* oocytes arrested at prophase. It is demonstrated that the authors of the paper provided no verifiable scientific results to support their pronouncements. The statements of the authors are misleading at best and dishonest at worse.

The authors of the paper/manuscript entitled "The M-phase regulatory phosphatase PP2A-B55 δ opposes protein kinase A on Arpp19 to initiate meiotic division", published in bioRxiv [bioRxiv (2019) doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1101/810549>] supposedly showed that *Xenopus* oocytes arrested at prophase enter meiotic division when Arpp19 was phosphorylated at serine 67 by Greatwall kinase causing Arpp19 to become an inhibitor of PP-2AB55 δ and that the latter is also the main protein phosphatase that can dephosphorylate Arpp19 at serine 109 that was due to PKA, a chemical reaction that is described as underlying progesterone induced dephosphorylation of Arpp19. Unfortunately for the authors concerned, they have provided no scientific evidence that showed that Arpp19 was a specific inhibitor of PP-2AB55 δ when Arpp19 was phosphorylated at serine 67 by Greatwall kinase and that Arpp-19 phosphorylated at serine 67 and Arpp19 phosphorylated at 109 are both specifically dephosphorylated by PP-2AB55 δ Arpp19. The concept that Arpp19 phosphorylated at serine 67 is both an inhibitor and a substrate of PP-2AB55 δ may have a foundation in science fiction but not in science.

Referring to the papers [1-4 the authors in the paper stated that "PP2A associated with the B55 δ subunit appears to be a major enzyme that dephosphorylates Cdk1 targets (Castilho et al., 2009; Mochida et al., 2009), hence controlling the downstream events of MPF activation: mitotic progression and mitotic exit. The regulation of PP2A-B55 δ depends on the kinase Gwl (Castilho et al., 2009; Vigneron et al., 2009). Once activated, Gwl directly phosphorylates two small related proteins, α -endosulfine or ARPP19, both of which then become able to interact with and inhibit PP2A-B55 δ (Gharbi-Ayachi et al., 2010; Mochida et al., 2010; Rangone et al., 2011). As a consequence, Cdk1 activity is no longer antagonized by PP2A-B55 δ phosphatase, resulting in an increased and stable level of phosphorylation of the mitotic substrates responsible for cell division (Glover, 2012; Haccard and Jessus, 2011; Lorca and Castro, 2013). Thus, without the contribution of Gwl inhibiting PP2A-B55 δ through ARPP19/ α -endosulfine, active Cyclin-B-Cdk1

can neither promote nor maintain the phosphorylation of its M-phase substrates". As stated in [5,6], the works described in [1-4] are at best misleading and at worse dishonest.

The obvious question that the authors should have asked was why they ruled out other forms of protein phosphatases, including PP-1 and especially PP-1_I which is an important form of PP-1. The authors of the paper did not do any experiments that showed that PP-2A-B55 δ played "an essential role during meiotic M-phase entry, not only by counteracting Cdk1 substrate phosphorylation but also by promoting Cdk1 activation. Once activated, it behaves as a major component of the MPF auto-amplification loop, rendering this process independent of PKA activity and independent of protein synthesis provided that a small amount Mos is present. Gwl/ARPP19/PP2A therefore not only regulates the events required for M-phase progression and exit, downstream of MPF, but also MPF activation per se and meiotic M-phase entry".

Ruling out PP-1 contradicts the seminal works of Huchon et al. [7] and Foulkes and Maller [8] which showed that a specific inhibitor of PP-1, namely protein phosphatase-1 inhibitor-1 (PP-1-I1) or PP-1-I2 delays the resumption of meiosis induced by progesterone but not by MPF in *Xenopus* oocytes implying the importance of a form of PP-1 in the resumption of meiosis. In view of the fact that the authors in the paper/manuscript did not do any work to rule out the role of any forms of PP-1 in the initiation, maintenance and ending of meiosis in *Xenopus* oocytes, they cannot scientifically state that no form of PP-1 was not involved.

Let us first enumerate the conclusory statements of the authors: It is stated that: (i) Importantly, Cdk1 activation also requires the inhibition of a specific phosphatase, the PP2A-B55 δ isoform, which counteracts Cdk1-dependent phosphorylations of mitotic/meiotic substrates, including Cdc25 and Myt17. PP2A-B55 δ inhibition is achieved by Arpp19, a specific inhibitor of this phosphatase when phosphorylated at S67 by the kinase Greatwall (Gwl)". As stated above, that phosphorylation of Arpp19 by Greatwall kinase at serine 67 converts it to a specific inhibitor of PP2A-B55 δ is a fallacy that is not based on concrete verifiable scientific data [5,6]. (ii) "In *Xenopus* oocyte, it is

clearly established that S67 phosphorylation of Arpp19 by Gwl promotes its binding to PP2A-B55 δ and the inhibition of the phosphatase". As stated above, that phosphorylation of Arpp19 by Greatwall kinase at serine 67 converts it to a specific inhibitor of PP2A-B55 δ is a fallacy that is not based on concrete scientific data [5,6]. (iii) "The molecular regulation of this last step, involving Gwl, Arpp19 and PP2A, has been well deciphered in mitosis and meiosis". "In *Xenopus* oocyte, it is clearly established that S67 phosphorylation of Arpp19 by Gwl promotes its binding to PP2A-B55 δ and the inhibition of the phosphatase". As stated above, the role of Arpp19 phosphorylated by Gwl at serine 67 as a specific inhibitor of PP-2A B55 δ is a fallacy that is not based on concrete scientific data [5,6]. (iii) "we identify PP2A-B55 δ as the phosphatase that dephosphorylates Arpp19 at S109, thus enabling oocytes to resume meiosis. The level of Arpp19 phosphorylated at S109 in prophase-arrested oocytes results from a balance between PKA and PP2A-B55 δ activities in favor of the kinase. Upon hormonal stimulation, PP2A-B55 δ activity remains unchanged while PKA is downregulated, leading to the partial dephosphorylation of Arpp19 at S109 that unlocks the prophase arrest. Therefore, the timing of meiosis resumption relies on the temporal coordination of S109 and S67 phosphorylations of Arpp19, orchestrated by one single phosphatase, PP2A-B55 δ , opposing two kinases, PKA and Gwl". The authors have not provided any shred of scientific evidence that proved that "PP2A-B55 δ was the protein phosphatase that dephosphorylated serine109 of Arpp19, that the dephosphorylation reaction was connected to resumption of meiosis, that the level of Arpp19 phosphorylated at S109 in prophase-arrested oocytes results from a balance between PKA and PP2A-B55 δ activities in favor of the kinase, that upon hormonal stimulation, PP2A-B55 δ activity remains unchanged while PKA is downregulated, leading to the partial dephosphorylation of Arpp19 at S109 that unlocks the prophase arrest and that the timing of meiosis resumption relies on the temporal coordination of S109 and S67 phosphorylations of Arpp19, orchestrated by one single phosphatase, PP2A-B55 δ , opposing two kinases, PKA and Gwl".

The authors of the paper stated that they found that PP-2AB55d was the protein phosphatase that was responsible for dephosphorylating serine 109 of ARPP19. GST-tagged Arpp19 previously *in vitro* phosphorylated at S109 by PKA (pS109-GST-Arpp19) was used as substrate to determine the activity of protein phosphatase(s). In Figure 1 of the paper, Western Immunoblotting was used to determine the protein phosphatase that acted on pS109-GST-Arpp19 following incubation with extracts of prophase *Xenopus* oocytes in the presence of 1 or 10 μM okadaic acid. The authors observed dephosphorylation of pS109-GST-Arpp19. However, 1 or 10 μM okadaic acid would not allow them to determine the nature of the protein phosphatase. It is note worthy that according to Figure 1C, almost ~30 % of total protein phosphatase activity was not inhibited by 10 μM okadaic acid, assuming that the authors knew how to assay for total protein phosphatase activity. A large proportion of PP-1 is in the form of PP-1_I which is inhibited by high concentration of ATP and requires Mg^{2+} and low concentration of ATP to exhibit full activity [7,8] and a large proportion of PP-2A is in its latent form and requires activating molecules to exhibit full activity [9-12]. The result of Figure 1C showed that ~30% of total protein phosphatase activity was not due to PP-1 and PP-2A, and that the amount of total protein phosphatase activity being measured was incorrect and misleading.

In Figure 2, ammonium sulfate precipitation was performed to apparently separate PP-1 and PP-2 activities. The result of Figure 2 was meant to show that PP-2A could be recovered with 40% ammonium sulfate precipitation which contained PP-2A and a small amount of PP-1 was the predominant protein phosphatase that acted upon pS109-GST-Arpp19. This statement was obviously misleading and erroneous since the specific activity of PP-1 is an order of magnitude higher than PP-2A. It is a concept of basic enzymology when one sees less protein, it does not mean that its activity is lower. The activity of an enzyme depends on its specific activity not on the amount of protein that one sees.

In Figure 3B, a Mono Q column was used to apparently separate the protein phosphatase activities that acted upon pS109-GST-Arpp19. The authors proclaimed that PP-2A-B55d

was the main protein phosphatase that acted upon pS109-GST-Arpp19. Unfortunately, the statement is misleading and possibly dishonest because: (i) the peak of activity does not coincide with the peak of protein represented by PP-2A-B55d. Most of the protein phosphatase activity was accounted by PP-2A-B56'- ϵ and also by PP-1, PP-4 and PP-6. It is quite puzzling that the authors did not probe for B55 α , B55 β , B55 γ and other B' and B'' subunits of PP-2A. As stated above, the authors have failed to assay for PP-1_I and PP-2A₀. The results of Figure 3B is therefore meaningless and the statement that PP-2A-B55d was the major protein phosphatase that dephosphorylated pS109-GST-Arpp19 is misleading at best and dishonest at worse.

In Figure 4, the authors of the paper used Fraction 5 from the eluates of the Mono Q column and loaded it onto a Phenyl Superose column followed by gel Filtration on Superose 10. Based on probing with anti-PP-2A-B55d antibodies, the authors concluded that they have isolated the main protein phosphatase that acted upon pS109-GST-Arpp19. It is quite puzzling that the authors did not probe for B55 α , B55 β , B55d and other B' and B'' subunits of PP-2A. The results of Figure 4 did not answer the question asked and the statement that PP-2A-B55d was the major protein phosphatase that dephosphorylated pS109-GST-Arpp19 was misleading at best and dishonest at worse. One can observe that PP-1 would be in the Flow Through Fractions of the Phenyl Superose Chromatography. Since the Flow Through Fractions were not analyzed and were discarded, PP-1 would not be observed in the subsequent Superose 10 Gel Filtration Chromatography.

In Figure 5, the authors of the paper used Fractions 7 and 8 from the eluates of the Mono Q column, pooled them and loaded them onto a Phenyl Superose Column followed by Gel Filtration on Superose 10. Based on probing with anti-PP-2A-B55d antibodies, the authors concluded that they have isolated the main protein phosphatase that acted upon pS109-GST-Arpp19. Again, it is quite puzzling that the authors did not probe for B55 α , B55 β , B55 γ and other B' and B'' subunits of the PP-2A. The results of Figure 5 did not show that PP-2A-B55d was the major protein phosphatase that dephosphorylated pS109-GST-Arpp19 and the statement that PP-2A-B55d was the major protein phosphatase that dephosphorylated pS109-GST-Arpp19 is misleading at best and dishonest at worse. In

fact, Figure 5 showed that a large proportion of the protein phosphatase that acted upon pS109-GST-Arpp19 was in fact a form of PP-1 because PP-1 is recovered in the Flow Through Fractions of the Phenyl Superose Chromatography and would not be observed in the subsequent Superose 10 Gel Filtration Chromatography. In order to show that a protein phosphatase is responsible for the dephosphorylation of serine 109 of Arpp19, proper Enzymology work and Enzyme Kinetics must be performed. The K_m and V_{max} of the dephosphorylation of pS109-GST-Arpp19 by various purified protein phosphatases including, PP-1C, PP-1_I, PP-2A-B55 α , PP-2A-B55 β , PP-2A-B55 γ , PP-2B and PP-2C, PP-4, PP-5 and PP-6 must be determined and compared.

In Figures 6, 7 and 8 of the paper, the authors purported to show and claim that they were measuring the activity of PP-2A-B55 δ , an assumption that is based solely on the results of Figures 3,4 and 5 which as indicated above are at best misleading and at worse dishonest. The authors have provided no scientific evidence that PP-2A-B55 δ is the protein phosphatase that dephosphorylated pS109-GST-Arpp19. In fact if the results of Figure 5 were to be believed and interpreted correctly, a form of PP-1 was also a major protein phosphatase that can dephosphorylate pS109-GST-Arpp19.

To then come up with a scheme that depicts Arpp19 as both an inhibitor and a substrate of PP-2A-B55 δ requires a lot of imagination and mental acrobatics that has more to do with science fiction than science. In the first part of the scheme depicted in Figure 9 of the paper, it was claimed that at prophase, PP-2A-B55 δ is responsible for the dephosphorylation of serines 67 and 109. The authors have provided zero scientific evidence that PP-2A-B55 δ is the enzyme that specifically dephosphorylated serines 67 and 109 of Arpp19 (See above). The only paper that alluded that a form of PP-2A, namely PP-2A-B55 α and not PP-2A-B55 δ is capable of dephosphorylating serine 67 of Arpp67 is itself riddled with anomalies and unscientific data [13]. As discussed in [5], the paper in question did not show that that PP-2A-B55 α was the protein phosphatase that dephosphorylated serine 67 of Arpp19.

In the second part of the scheme, it was showed that upon stimulation with progesterone, PKA is inhibited, resulting in dephosphorylation of serine 109 of Arpp19 by PP-2A-B55d. As stated above, the authors have provided zero scientific evidence that PP-2A-B55d was the enzyme that specifically dephosphorylated serines 109 of Arpp19. In order to show that of PP-2A-B55d is the protein phosphatase that dephosphorylate serines 67 and 109 of Arpp19, the authors must determine K_m and V_{max} values for the dephosphorylation of pure Arpp19 phosphorylated at serine 67 and pure Arpp19 phosphorylated at serine 109 by PP-1c, PP-1i, PP-2Ac, PP-2A₂, PP-2A-B55 α , PP-2A-B55 β , PP-2A-B55 γ , PP-2A-B55d, different forms of PP-2A-B', different forms of PP-2A-B'', PP-2B, PP-2C, PP-4, PP-5 and PP-6, and compare the generated K_m and V_{max} values.

In the third part of the scheme, the authors of the paper stated that Greatwall kinase phosphorylates Arpp19 at serine 67 converting it to a specific inhibitor of PP-2A-B55d. As stated above, the evidence that showed that Arpp19 phosphorylated at serine 67 was a specific inhibitor of PP-2A-B55d is misleading at best and dishonest at worse. In order to show that Arpp19 phosphorylated at serine 67 is a specific inhibitor of PP-2A-B55d, the authors must do proper Enzymology and Enzyme Kinetics work. They must do the following: (i) Show that pure Arpp67 phosphorylated at serine 67 is a specific inhibitor of pure preparations of PP-2A-B55d and not of pure preparations of PP-1c, PP-1i, PP-2Ac, PP-2A₂, PP-2A-B55 α , PP-2A-B55 β , PP-2A-B55 γ , different forms of PP-2A-B', different forms of PP-2A-B'', PP-2B, PP-2C, PP-4, PP-5 and PP-6 (ii) Plot proper Dose Response Inhibitory Curve of % of Control v. Concentration of pure Arpp19 phosphorylated at serine 67 and determine the IC_{50} of each inhibition (iii) determine the inhibition of PP-2A-B55d by pure Arpp19 phosphorylated at serine 67 using a number of at least 5 different substrates to show that the effect of Arpp19 phosphorylated at serine 67 is not substrate directed but enzyme directed.

The authors of the paper concluded that "initiation of meiosis by progesterone in *Xenopus* oocytes occurs via inhibition of PKA but that PP-2A-B55d is not activated". The authors admit that they could not show the binding of Arpp19 phosphorylated at

serine 109 to PP-2A-B55d nor can they show any effect of Arpp19 phosphorylated at serine 109 on PP-2A-B55d activity. "Phosphorylation of serine 67 of Arpp19 by Greatwall kinase converts Arpp19 into a specific inhibitor of PP-2A-B55d". The requirement for the dephosphorylation of serine 109 of Arpp19 by PP-2A-B55d is contrary to the initial supposition that Arpp phosphorylated on serine 67 by Greatwall kinase becomes a specific inhibitor of PP-2A-B55d. PP-2A-B55d cannot be active and inhibited at the same time during the resumption of meiosis.

The scheme provided by the authors is not based on verifiable scientific results and inexplicably ignored the seminal work of Huchon et al. [14] which showed that PP-1-I1 which becomes a specific inhibitor of PP-1 when it is phosphorylated on threonine 35 by PKA interferes with Progesterone effect in *Xenopus* oocytes arrested at prophase and the paper by Foulkes and Maller [15] which showed that PP-1-I2 delays the effect of progesterone in *Xenopus* oocytes arrested at prophase, nor can the scheme be reconciled with the work of Duckworth et al. [16] which showed that (i) Cdc25, the activator of Cdk1 is itself phosphorylated by PKA on serine 287 which inhibited Cdc25, (ii) serine 287 is dephosphorylated in response to progesterone just before cdc2 dephosphorylation and M-phase entry, (iii) high PKA activity maintains phosphorylation of Ser-287 *in vivo*, and (iv) inhibition of PKA by its heat-stable inhibitor (PKI) induces dephosphorylation of Ser-287, and the work of Pirino et al. [17]. Why the authors of the paper deliberately ignored PP-1-Inhibitor-1 which is a key substrate of PKA in the cell is beyond comprehension.

The scheme provided by the authors is in stark contradiction with the work of Adhikari et al. [18] which showed that (i) Mastl kinase (equivalent of Greatwall kinase) was not required for the resumption of meiosis and progression to metaphase I in mouse oocytes, (ii) Mastl-deficient oocytes did not fail to progress through meiosis I but underwent GVBD with kinetics and efficiencies that were indistinguishable from those of Mastl^{+/+} oocytes, (iii) Mastl has no essential role during meiotic resumption or prometaphase I progression in mouse oocytes, (iii) there might be some slight differences in the timing of completion of meiosis I between control and mutant oocytes *in vivo*, (iv) Mastl was

required for the timely activation of APC/C that was needed for the completion of meiosis I in mouse oocytes, (v) The activation of spindle assembly checkpoint occurred normally in *Mastl* deficient oocytes, (vi) The level of Cdc20 in *Matl* deficient oocytes remained low compared to normal oocytes, (vii) *Mastl* was essential for MII entry, (viii) *Mastl* was not required for the upregulation of Cdk1 activity during prometaphase I but was required for entry in MII, (ix) PP-2A activity in both *Mastl* deficient and normal oocytes were comparable at GV and GVBD stages, implying that mouse oocytes progress through metaphase I without the suppression of PP-2A activity and that *Mastl* did not regulate PP-2A activity during prometaphase I, and (x) *Mastl* likely play an essential role in triggering the activation of APC/C that is required for the down regulation of Cdk1 activity that might mediate the timely onset of anaphase I in mouse oocytes.

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